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AN ATTITUDE & KNOWLEDGE OF PHARMACISTS TOWARDS PHARMACOVIGILANCE & ADR REPORTING AND BARRIERS - A CURRENT SCENARIO IN TAMILNADU

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ABSTRACT

Background: An adverse drug reaction (ADR) is associate degree injury caused by taking a medicine. The Study entitled “An Attitude & Knowledge of pharmacists towards pharmacovigilance & Adr reporting and barriers in current scenario; in Tamilnadu” was designed to assess the awareness of Pharmacovigilance and ADR reporting. Methods: This was a prospective cross sectional study involving registered community pharmacists and hospital pharmacists to evaluate the knowledge, perception and practice of pharmacovigilance which was conducted by face to face questionnaire over a period of 6 month duration included a total 274 (78%) participants out of 350. Results: Out of the total participants 222(81.02%) had fair knowledge about ADR, 79(28.83%) had fair knowledge, about pharmacovigilance. 68 (25.09%) of participants were aware of National Pharmacovigilance Programme in India, 41 (14.96%) of participants knew how to report an ADR and 112(40.87%) of participants knew when and what to be report as ADR. 245(84.41%) of pharmacists believed that the ADR reporting should be mandatory for pharmacists. Among the participants 78(28.46%) of pharmacists only had facility for ADR reporting. 212(77.37%) of participants unaware of existence of national adr reporting system. Conclusion: This survey on pharmacovigilance and ADR reporting among pharmacists in Tamilnadu suggests that the pharmacist may lack in-depth understanding of the facts about ADR reporting and may need more information on the National Pharmacovigilance System and ADR reporting process. Since there is a need of educational programs about ADR reporting and pharmacovigilance in the pharmacy.

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INTRODUCTION

The World Health Organization (WHO) defined ADR as any response to a drug that is noxious and unintended, and that occurs at doses used in humans for prophylaxis, diagnosis, or therapy, excluding failure to accomplish the intended purpose. ADRs are responsible for a significant number of hospital admissions ranging from 0.3% to 11%. ADRs can cause short and long-term hospitalization and mortality (WHO 1972).^[12]

An adverse drug event (ADE) is an injury resulting from medical intervention related to a drug.¹This includes medication errors, adverse drug reactions, allergic reactions, and overdoses. ADEs can happen anywhere: in hospitals, long-term care settings, and outpatient settings.^[2]

Pharmacovigilance is a part of patient care and patient safety that ensures the best use of medicines for the treatment or prevention of adverse drug reactions. According to World Health Organization (WHO) pharmacovigilance is the science and activities relating to the detection, assessment, understanding and prevention of adverse effects or any other drug-related problem.^[12]

The success of a pharmacovigilance program depends upon the involvement of the healthcare professionals and reporting the ADRs. Being the key healthcare professionals, the doctors, nurses and pharmacists have immense responsibility in reporting ADRs and strengthening the pharmacovigilance mechanisms that exists in their vicinity. The pharmacist's role is to promote the development, maintenance and ongoing evaluation of a program to reduce the risks of ADRs by detecting, reporting and assessing any suspected ADRs. A pharmacist can educate the physicians and nurses and can encourage compliance with the ADR reporting program.^[15]

The ADR reporting rate in India is below 1% compared to the worldwide rate of 5%. Given the lower rate in India, one of the reasons might be attributed to the awareness about pharmacovigilance and ADR monitoring among the Indian healthcare providers. In India, the Drugs Control Department within the Ministry of Health and Family Welfare initiated the establishment of a nationwide network to build a comprehensive Pharmacovigilance data system in 2004. The National Pharmacovigilance Programme (NPP) of India is sponsored by the WHO. NPP in

India is divided in a three tier structure into 2 zonal centers, 5 regional centers and 24 peripheral centers. There are two zonal centers which collate information from all over the country and send it to the Uppsala Monitoring Centre in Sweden. The central drug standard control organization (CDSCO), Directorate General of Health Services, Government of India in collaboration with Indian Pharmacopoeia commission, Ghaziabad initiating a National wide Pharmacovigilance programme for protecting the health of patients by assuring drug safety. Pharmacovigilance programme of india lacks continuity due to lack of awareness and inadequate training about drug safety monitoring among healthcare professionals in India.^[28] ADR reports collected from the affiliated medical colleges will be consigned to the national coordinating center and thereby casualty assessment will be conducted and upload the reports into the pharmacovigilance software. Finally, the integrated ADR data will be transmitted through vigiflow software interface into the Uppsala Monitoring Center's ADR database where signal processing will be carried out.^[7]

The Central Drugs Standard Control Organization (CDSCO) in India has banned the manufacture and sale of more than 300 fixed dose drug combination to prevent the misuse of drugs and to prevent drug resistance in March 2016. A gazette notification by Ministry of Health and Family Welfare was issued on 10th March 2016 to ban these fixed drug combinations. The list includes common cough syrup solutions, analgesics and antibiotic combinations. Several drugs that are prohibited or withdrawn from other countries like the United States are still widely available in India. Some of these include the following: Painkillers - Oxyphenbutazone, Nimesulide, Propoxyphene. Antibacterials - Furazolidone, Nitrofurazone. Anabolic Steroid - Nandrolone decanoate. Drugs Acting on the Brain - Thioridazine, Pergolide, Pemoline. Cholesterol Lowering Drug – Cerivastatin. Constipation – Phenolphthalein. Human Placental Extract.^[3] Since 2017, 444 drugs were prohibited for manufacture and sale through gazette notifications under section 26A of drugs & cosmetics act 1940 by the ministry of health and family welfare.^[4]

Pharmacovigilance is still in its formative years in India. This may be due to ignorance, lack of awareness by healthcare professionals and lack of training about drug safety monitoring that leads to insufficient data of local population and reliance on the data collected in other countries. The prospective pharmacy practitioners need to be well trained on how to recognize, prevent, and report ADR. Few studies have been conducted to evaluate pharmacy students' knowledge and attitudes about ADR reporting.^[27] Therefore, the present study was conducted with the aim to evaluate the an attitude & knowledge of pharmacists towards pharmacovigilance & adr reporting and barriers in current scenario; in Tamilnadu.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Materials used:

- Informed Consent Form
- KAP questionnaire

Study design and site:

The six months prospective cross sectional Knowledge Attitude Practice (KAP) Questionnaire based study was carried out in Tamilnadu (Erode, Namakkal, Salem, Coimbatore), from July to December 2017. A questionnaire was prepared to inspect knowledge, attitude and practices and barriers of pharmacists about ADR reporting.

Study sample:

A total of 274 pharmacists (Registered and non-registered) participated in the study, The study criteria included pharmacists of Community and Hospital.

Inclusion and exclusion criteria:

All the pharmacists working in the hospital and community pharmacy during the study period were included. The pharmacists who were not willing to participate in the study and the ones who were on leave were excluded.

Design of Questionnaire:

The questionnaire was a 24 item inventory titled Standard KAP questionnaire, the items were generated from the literature and adaptation from previous studies. KAP questionnaire that included the demographics and a total of 28 survey items organized into two sections including 8 questions related to knowledge, 6 questions related to attitude, 8 questions related to practice and 2 questions related to barriers.

Data collection:

Initially KAP questionnaire was administered and briefed to all participants about the purpose of the study and asked to submit the same. The KAP questionnaire was analyzed question wise and their percentage value was calculated.

RESULTS

Out of 350 KAP questionnaires circulated, all (community and hospital) pharmacists in Tamilnadu responded and involved in the KAP survey questionnaires. The overall response of the pharmacists in filling the KAP was not good and most of them didn't have enough time to answer the questions. Among the 350 pharmacists selected for the study, only 274 responded and were involved in the KAP survey.

Table. 1. Demographic detail of the participants.

S.NO	DEMOGRAPHIC DETAILS	NO. OF PARTICIPANTS (N = 274)	
		Male	Female
01	Gender wise distribution	161 (58.75%)	113 (41.24%)
02	Age		
	20-30	152(55.47%)	
	31-40	79(28.83%)	
	41-50	31(11.31%)	
	51-60	12(4.37%)	
03	Qualification		
	D.Pharm	162 (59.12%)	
	B.Pharm	19 (6.93%)	
	Others	93 (33.94%)	
04	Experience in dispensing in years?		
	0-1	101(36.86%)	
	3.1-6	74(27%)	
	>6	99(36.13%)	

Table. 2. Knowledge, attitude, practice of pharmacists towards Pharmacovigilance & ADR reporting Questionnaire.

S.NO	K A P ITEMS	KAP RESPONSES (%) N = 274
01	No. of prescription dispensed per day ?	
	< 20	65(23.72%)
	21 – 30	141(51.45%)
	>10	68(24.81%)
02	No. of patients served per day including OTC?	
	< 30	89(32.48%)
	31 – 50	118(43.06%)
	>50	67(24.45%)
03	Can you define term Pharmacovigilance?	
	Answered	79(28.83%)
	Not Answered	195(71.16%)
04	Can you define ADR?	
	Answered	222(81.02%)
	Not Answered	52(18.97%)
05	Are you aware of National Pharmacovigilance Program in India?	
	Yes	68(25.09%)
	No	206(75.18%)
06	Do you consider ADR's reporting as a duty for a pharmacist?	
	Yes	245(84.41%)
	No	29(10.58%)
07	Do you think reporting ADR is necessary?	
	Yes	198(72.26%)
	No	76(27.73%)
08	It is important for community pharmacist to attend training program in Pharmacovigilance?	
	Yes	201(73.35%)
	No	73(26.64%)
09	ADR should be reported only when they are,	
	Serious & life threatening	105(38.35%)
	Serious & Cause disability	29(10.58%)
	Mild & Cause less	28(10.21%)
	All of the Conditions	112(40.87%)
10	Do you believe reporting ADR will improve patients safety?	
	Yes	216(78.83%)
	No	58(21.16%)
11	Does your workplace provide information regarding the procedures of reporting ADR's?	
	Yes	78(28.46%)
	No	196(71.53%)
12	Is ADR reporting form is available at your workplace?	
	Yes	78(28.46%)
	No	196(71.53%)
13	Do you know how to report an ADR?	
	Yes	41(14.96%)
	No	233(85.03%)
14	Have you ever reported an ADR?	
	Yes	0
	No	274(100%)
15	To whom did you send your spontaneous report?	
	Reported	0
	Not reported	274(100%)
16	Do you feel that you are adequately trained in ADR reporting?	
	Yes	39(14.23%)
	No	235(85.76%)
17	It is necessary to report ADR's of OTC products supplied in my pharmacy?	
	Yes	207(75.54%)
	No	67(24.45%)
18	Due to severe ADR recently banned drug in India?	
	Know	109(39.78%)

	Don't know	165(60.21%)
19	Reporting of ADR is important to show patients that their concerns are taken seriously?	
	Yes	97(35.40%)
	No	177(64.56%)
20	Have you ever read any article related to ADR's in the last 12 months?	
	Yes	78(28.46%)
	No	196(71.53%)
21	Have you seen any patient experiencing an ADR?	
	Yes	34(12.40%)
	No	240(87.59%)
22	You ever counseled patient regarding ADR's in last 12 months for following:	
	Food – Drug interaction	95(34.67%)
	Drug – Drug interaction	58(21.16%)
	Not counseled	121(44.16%)
23	Which of the problems do you face while reporting ADR's in your workplace?	
	Lack of information provide by patients	27(9.85%)
	Pharmacist doesn't have time fear of facing legal problems	17(6.20%)
	Unaware of existence of national ADR reporting system	212(77.37%)
	Others	18(6.56%)
24	What is in your opinion the most discouraging factor for reporting?	
	Lack of time	37(13.50%)
	Lack of awareness	174(63.50%)
	No response	63(22.99%)

Table 3: Banned drugs Responded.

BRAND NAME	NO.OF DRUGS REPORTED
Corex Syrup	11
Rexcof syrup	25
Codistar syrup	13
Linctus codeine syrup	6
Tab.Nimesulide	20
Ascoril C syrup	6
Tab.Pioz - MF	2
Phensedyl cough linctus	2
Tab.Glimistar M1	4
Vicks Action 500	2
others	22

DISCUSSION

The survey questionnaire was designed and prepared by referring previous studies conducted in worldwide. According to our knowledge, this is the first survey in Tamilnadu state to evaluate an attitude & knowledge of pharmacists towards pharmacovigilance & ADR reporting and barriers in current scenario. However, the main limitation of the study was the response rate from community and hospital pharmacists was found to be 78.28%. The low participation rate in the study and failure to answer some questions (especially for the definition of pharmacovigilance and ADR) may be due to poor knowledge of the term 'pharmacovigilance'. The ADR reporting rate was found to be nil in our study. In order to maximize the response rate and minimize response bias, the questionnaire was administered personally to the participants by the facilitator ^[4].

In our study, focus to increase the participant's (pharmacists) awareness to Pharmacovigilance topics, monitoring of ADRs, and the national- scenario on Pharmacovigilance. This educational intervention program encouraged the participants (pharmacists) to pursue career in Pharmacovigilance as their future perspective. The comparison between the socio demographic details of the respondents showed that the pharmacists within the age group of 21-30 years and with least experience had more knowledge about ADRs and pharmacovigilance compared to elder respondents with age group of 51-60 years and experience with more than 20 years. On the other hand, the parameters like gender, qualification did not have any significant difference in the knowledge of the respondents. However, attitudes are potentially modifiable variables. Hence, Mahendra Kumar BJ ^[4] has shown that an educational program can significantly modify pharmacist reporting related attitudes and influence the ADR reporting behavior into a positive manner.

In the study reported that the reasons for not reporting the ADRs were lack of time, different care priorities, uncertainty about the drug causing ADR, difficulty in accessing forms, lack of awareness of requirements for reporting and lack of understanding the purpose of spontaneous reporting systems.^[4] In our study, the explanation for not reporting ADRs by the pharmacists was similar to the above mentioned reasons. Evidently, the documented results of question 07(28.83%) & 09(25.09%) which strongly suggested pharmacists are in need of knowledge regarding the Pharmacovigilance Program of India (PVPI). Question 08 (81.02%) & 13(40.87%) & 18(0%) & 22(39.78%) & 23(35.40%) & 24(28.46%) which strongly suggested pharmacists are in need of knowledge regarding about the National scenario on ADR reporting system, where there was an increased positive response rate. The result strongly suggests educating pharmacists about the reporting systems of ADRs both of National and International standards^[4].

The documented results of question 10(89.42%) & 11 (72.26%) & 12(73.35%) & 11 (72.26%) & 14(78.83%) & 20(14.23%) & 21(75.54%) which strongly suggested pharmacists are in need of attitude regarding the National scenario on ADR reporting system and Pharmacovigilance Program of India (PVPI).

The documented results of regarding the practice questions were 05 & 06 & 15 (28.46%) & 16(28.46%) & 18(0%) & 19(0%) & 21(12.40%) & 22. The study secondarily focused on improvising the approach on barriers among the pharmacists, Question 23 and 24 of table 02 emphasized on role of barriers on ADR reporting KAP defined effective questionnaire.

In the developing countries, since the pharmacists are free healthcare consultants and they are easily accessed, patients always prefer to contact pharmacists in case of any drug suspected reaction. Therefore, pharmacists need to be actively involved in the surveillance of drug safety issues within the context of their practices. The pharmacist's role in pharmacovigilance may vary from country to country, but the professional responsibility is the same.^[4]

CONCLUSION

The results of the present study showed that the majority of the pharmacists have insufficient knowledge about ADRs and pharmacovigilance program. Since there is a need of pharmacovigilance in the pharmacy, under and postgraduate educational programs about ADR reporting and pharmacovigilance practice need to be included in the curriculum to improve ADR reporting.

This survey on pharmacovigilance and ADR reporting among pharmacists in Tamilnadu suggests that the pharmacist in this state may lack in-depth understanding of the facts about ADR reporting and may need more information on the National Pharmacovigilance System and ADR reporting process. Pharmacist's education should include topics related to the methods of detecting, preventing, and reporting of ADRs to enable and play vital role in prevention of ADRs through their interactions with both prescribers and patients.

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